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One Day FDP on
"MODERN METHODS OF ONLINE TEACHING"

Certificate

This is to certify that Mr/Ms/Mrs _____ Dr.Abdul Musref Khan
has participated in One Day Faculty Development Programme on **“MODERN METHODS OF ONLINE TEACHING”** held on 19th July- 2020 organized by the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Nalanda Institute of Engineering and Technology, Sattenapalli.

Mr. B. KISHORE KUMAR
Convener
Assoc.Professor & Head, ME

DR. S. DEVIKALA
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